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Mechanical, Self-sensing, and Biological Characteristics of Additively Manufactured Multifunctional PEEK Composite Scaffolds

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Outline

Introduction

Motivation and
scope of the
study

Synthesis and
characterization
of feedstock

Fused Filament
Fabrication (FFF)
of PEEK cellular
composites

Mechanical and
Piezoresistive
testing

Biological
characterization

Conclusion and
ongoing work

Introduction – Additive manufacturing (AM) of Orthopaedic PEEK implants

- Orthopaedic implants global market value \$47.2 billion in 2022²
- Titanium alloys used as gold standard, with polyetheretherketone (PEEK) emerging for spinal-, joint-, trauma-, and arthroscopic implants
 - High-performance thermoplastic for a wide range of applications, including aerospace, automotive, and **biomedical**
 - High strength and stiffness properties
 - **Biocompatible**, chemically resistant, **bio-inert**, wear resistant, **radiolucent**
 - enables fabrication of biocompatible and mechanically stable patient-specific implants, utilising AM
 - AM via FFF of PEEK remains challenging as it processes above 343 °C

Introduction – Cellular structures

← Periodic (fully ordered) → Random (disordered)

Gibson LJ et al, 2010

Geißendörfer et al, 2014

Open-cell, closed-cell, Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS)

Natural foams, e.g. cedar, cork

Random foam

→ Graded porous implants to reduce stress-shielding and bone resorption

High surface area density (mm^2/mm^3) promotes favourable bone cell proliferation, attachment and rate of osseointegration

Introduction – self-sensing composites

- By integrating nanofillers like **carbon nanotubes** (CNTs) and **graphene nanoplatelets** (GNPs), polymers can be rendered electrically conductive, transforming them into self-sensing composites.
- Material itself is capable of sensing strain and damage – **piezoresistivity** can be leveraged
- In the early stages of deformation the gauge factor, k , is a measure of the materials sensitivity of the relative change in electrical resistance, R , to mechanical strain, ε , with

$$k = \frac{\Delta(\Delta R/R_0)}{\Delta L/L_0}$$

- Applications in structural health monitoring, condition-based maintenance, or smart materials

Cover art: J. Schneider

Aim of the work

- i. Development of novel nanomodified PEEK composites:
 - PEEK (neat), PEEK/CNT 6 weight percent (wt.%), PEEK/CNT/GNP 2×2.5 wt.%, PEEK/GNP 5 wt.%
- ii. Modelling and 3D printing of PEEK cellular composites
 - Porosity: 63%, 56%, 41%
- iii. Assessment of mechanical and piezoresistive performance of cellular scaffolds under compressive loading
- iv. Analysis of surface characteristics of scaffolds
- v. Assessment of *in vitro* biological response of 3D printed scaffolds of PEEK nanocomposites

An Overview

Filament Extrusion

Pore size:	720 μm	470 μm	200 μm
Relative density:	$\bar{\rho} = 46\%$	$\bar{\rho} = 55\%$	$\bar{\rho} = 73\%$

Scaffolds for mechanical tests

Scaffolds for biomedical tests

5 mm

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF)

Compression Testing

Biological Characterisation

Results & Discussion

- a) Mechanical and piezoresistive performance evaluation through
 - I. Quasi-static compression testing up to densification
 - II. Quasi-static cyclic compression testing, strain-controlled ($\Delta\varepsilon = 3\%$ with $\varepsilon_{max} = 5\%$)
- b) Biological characterisation
 - I. Surface modification through sulfonation
 - II. **In vitro assays for cytotoxicity, cell proliferation and cell differentiation** were performed to assess the influence of scaffold material and porosity on bone cell precursors.

Cell Seeding and Culture	Viability Assay	Proliferation Assay	Alkaline Phosphatase Assay
MC3T3-E1 (murine osteoblast precursors) cultured over 14 days. Samples analysed on 1st, 7th and 14th day	Indicates metabolic activity of cells, denotes percentage of cells alive in presence of scaffolds, evaluates cytotoxicity	DNA quantification determines rate of cell multiplication in presence of scaffolds	Cell differentiation marker, indicates mature bone cell formation, can be used to map bone tissue regeneration

SEM imaging of cryogenically fractured surfaces/ 3D-printed lattice

Presence and uniform dispersion of CNTs/GNPs in PEEK matrix

Mechanical and Piezoresistive characteristics under quasi-static compression: 3D printed scaffolds

- Stress-Strain response dictated by 3 regimes: linear elastic, plastic and densification
- Corresponding piezoresistive regimes:
- Resistance decreases initially until yielding of the material (improvement of conductive paths), and then increases up to densification regime (disruption of conductive paths due to crack formation) - composites with CNTs
- Resistance decreases steadily until densification for PEEK/GNP5 composites (becomes fully conductive)
- Collapse of ligaments govern piezo-resistance

Mechanical and Piezoelectric testing (QS)

➔
Mechanical performance increases with decreasing porosity

←
Decreasing piezoresistive sensitivity for PEEK/CNT6
→
Increasing piezoresistive sensitivity for PEEK/GNP5
←
Low piezoresistive sensitivity for PEEK/CNT/GNP2.5

Mechanical and Piezoresistive behaviour under quasi-static cyclic compression: 3D printed scaffolds

$\Delta\varepsilon = 3\%$, $\varepsilon_{max} = 5\%$, Cycle count: 500 \rightarrow approaching fatigue limit at 500 cycles

Results: Biological characterization

- Percentage cell viability, measured from fluorescence-based resazurin assay; cellular metabolism reaches a peak specific to the material and geometry
- Scaffolds support cell survival in selected cases
- Cell proliferation, determined by DNA quantification; DNA content reaches an overall maxima by day 7
- Favourable cell proliferation observed in PEEK/CNT/GNP/2.5 on day 7
- Elevated ALP expression observed consistently through days 7 to 14; indicates successful cell differentiation in presence of scaffolds

Conclusions and ongoing work

- Successfully fabricated architected PEEK nanocomposite scaffolds with micro-scale features using in-house nanoengineered feedstocks comprising CNTs and/or GNPs
- The tuneable self-sensing and mechanical performance of PEEK composite lattices were experimentally demonstrated by varying their architectural parameters in addition to the filler content/type with a particular focus on strain and damage sensing.
- Successful cell survival, proliferation and cell differentiation observed in scaffolds over a 14-day span of cell culture under *in vitro* conditions.
- Further *in vitro* analytical procedures can be explored to visualize cell behavior in the scaffolds in real-time; Can enable prediction of their biological potential *in vivo*
- Finite element studies are being carried out to predict the mechanical and piezoresistive performance and to develop a predictive capability

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Thank you.

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